

THE IMPLEMENTATION OF INCLUSIVE EDUCATION IN CABAGAN DISTRICT: ITS OPPORTUNITIES AND CHALLENGES

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the implementation of inclusive education in Cabagan District and identified the opportunities and challenges encountered by school heads and teachers during School Year 2024–2025. Using a descriptive survey design, the study was conducted in 26 public elementary schools in Cabagan, Isabela, with 286 respondents composed of 20 school heads and 266 teachers. Data were gathered through survey questionnaires and analyzed using frequency and percentage, weighted mean, and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). Findings revealed that the implementation of inclusive education was generally highly implemented, with a grand mean of 3.32. Curriculum design, teaching methodologies and strategies, learning space and environment, and classroom assessment were rated highly implemented, while learning resources were rated implemented. Opportunities in inclusive education were always observed, with an overall mean of 3.35, particularly in governance support and teacher professional development. However, challenges were generally rated serious, with an overall mean of 2.59. The most pressing concerns involved resource availability and infrastructure, policy and implementation, and collaboration between teachers and parents, while teacher preparedness was moderately serious. Results further showed no significant difference in the perceptions of school heads and teachers regarding opportunities and challenges. However, a significant difference was found in teachers' perceptions of inclusive education implementation when grouped according to years of service. The study concludes that while inclusive education in Cabagan District is progressing positively, strengthened training, improved resources, stronger policy implementation, and

enhanced school-home collaboration are necessary to sustain and improve inclusive practices for diverse and marginalized learners across participating schools.

Keywords: *Inclusive education implementation, marginalized learners, instructional adaptation, institutional support, Cabagan District*

INTRODUCTION

Education is a fundamental human right, and inclusive education seeks to ensure that this right is realized for all learners regardless of ability, background, or condition (UNESCO, 2026). Globally, inclusive education is increasingly recognized as essential to building more equitable and caring societies because it requires education systems to respond to individual learner needs and to ensure that all learners participate and achieve together. In practice, inclusive education means that children, including those with disabilities, should have access to the resources, support, and accommodations they need to learn effectively. However, this goal remains difficult to achieve, as many children with disabilities and other marginalized learners continue to face exclusion from education, especially in contexts marked by poverty, discrimination, displacement, and crisis (UNICEF, 2025; UNESCO, 2020).

In the Philippines, the education system is anchored on the policy that all citizens have the right to quality basic education and that schools must serve the needs of all learners (Republic Act No. 9155, 2001). This commitment has been strengthened by Republic Act No. 11650, which institutionalizes inclusion and services for learners with disabilities in support of inclusive education, and by DepEd Order No. 44, s. 2021, which provides policy guidelines on educational programs and services for learners with disabilities in the K to 12 basic education program (Department of Education [DepEd], 2021; Republic Act No. 11650, 2022). Inclusive education, therefore, recognizes learner diversity and calls for responsive teaching, differentiated support, and appropriate educational pathways so that learners with varying needs and circumstances can participate meaningfully in school (DepEd, 2021; UNESCO, 2026).

Republic Act No. 7277, or the *Magna Carta for Disabled Persons*, as later amended to use the title *Magna Carta for Persons with Disability* under Republic Act No. 9442, laid an important legal foundation for protecting the rights of persons with disabilities in the Philippines (Republic Act No. 7277, 1992; Republic Act No. 9442, 2007). This legal framework underscores the State's duty to support the rehabilitation, self-development, self-reliance, and social integration of persons with disabilities, while more recent legislation specifically requires equitable access to quality education and appropriate support for learners with disabilities (Republic Act No. 11650, 2022). Thus, the Philippine policy environment affirms that educational planning, school services, and learner support should be responsive to the needs of persons with disabilities rather than treating them as peripheral to the mainstream education system (Republic Act No. 11650, 2022; UNESCO, 2026).

DepEd Order No. 44, s. 2021, titled *Policy Guidelines on the Provision of Educational Programs and Services for Learners with Disabilities in the K to 12 Basic Education Program*, provides comprehensive guidance for implementing inclusive and equitable education for learners with disabilities (DepEd, 2021). The policy affirms learners' right to access quality education and directs schools to provide appropriate placements, programs, and support mechanisms that respond to diverse learner needs. The later dissemination of the implementing rules and regulations of Republic Act No. 11650 further reinforced the national commitment to operationalizing inclusive education in schools and communities (DepEd, 2025; Republic Act No. 11650, 2022).

In the municipality of Cabagan, the Local Government Unit has also taken part in supporting inclusive education through the establishment of an Inclusive Learning Resource Center (ILRC). According to the Philippine Information Agency, Cabagan formally inaugurated its ILRC in Barangay Catabayungan in September 2025, and the facility was intended to provide tailored educational and therapeutic services for children with special needs (Edale, 2025). This local initiative reflects the principle of shared governance in education, wherein local actors help translate national education policy into programs and services that fit community needs (Republic Act No. 9155, 2001). Consistent with DepEd policy, ILRCs are designed as support systems for learners, teachers, school personnel, and other stakeholders in the delivery of appropriate educational services to learners with disabilities (DepEd, 2021).

The researcher conducted the study to examine the implementation of inclusive education and the opportunities and challenges faced by school heads and teachers in carrying out the program. Teachers and parents are crucial stakeholders in inclusive education because effective inclusion depends not only on policy but also on classroom practices, family involvement, and coordinated support for learners (DepEd, 2021; UNESCO, 2026). Through this study, the researcher aims to identify the opportunities and challenges in implementing inclusive education and to propose support mechanisms that may help schools address emerging concerns more effectively.

Moreover, the researcher was motivated to conduct this study based on her experience in a particular school, where she handled a class that included a learner who was physically different from the others. This experience encouraged the researcher to examine more closely how inclusive education is implemented in the Cabagan District, as well as the opportunities and challenges encountered in practice. As a member of the Local School Board, the researcher believes that equality and equity should be promoted for all children, especially those from marginalized groups, since inclusive education is premised on the recognition that all learners can learn and that diversity should be treated as an asset rather than a barrier (UNESCO, 2026; UNICEF, 2025). From this perspective, learners should not be isolated because, regardless of their condition, each child has abilities and potential that can be developed not only for personal survival but also for meaningful participation in society.

Research Questions

This study aimed to unravel the implementation of inclusive education in Cabagan district, its opportunities and challenges for the school year 2024-2025. More specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the school heads and teachers in terms of:
 - a) years in service
 - b) training attended in inclusive education in the last five years
 - c) highest educational attainment
2. How is inclusive education being implemented in Cabagan District as perceived by the school heads and teachers in terms of:
 - a) curriculum design: competency and content
 - b) teaching methodologies and strategies
 - c) learning space and environment
 - d) learning resources
 - e) classroom assessment
3. Is there a significant difference in the perception of the school heads and teachers in the implementing inclusive education: when grouped according to profile?
4. What are the opportunities encountered by the school heads and teachers in the implementation of inclusive education in Cabagan District in terms of:
 - a) partnerships in inclusion
 - b) governance support
 - c) teacher professional development
5. How serious are the challenges encountered by the school heads and the teachers in the implementation of inclusive education in Cabagan District in terms of:
 - a) teacher preparedness
 - b) resource availability and infrastructure
 - c) policy and implementation
 - d) collaboration
6. Is there a significant difference in the opportunities and challenges encountered by the school heads and teachers?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

To achieve the purpose or the objective of the study, the descriptive survey method was used. According to Singh (2023), a descriptive study is a methodological approach that seeks to depict the characteristics of a phenomenon or subject under investigation. In scientific inquiry, it serves as a foundational tool for researchers aiming to observe, record, and analyze the intricate details of a particular topic. This method provides a rich

and detailed account that aids in understanding, categorizing, and interpreting the subject matter.”

This type of research is deemed appropriate for the study because it seeks to describe and analyze the opportunities and challenges in the implementation of inclusive education in Cabagan District.

Locale of the Study

This study was conducted in selected public elementary schools in the Cabagan District, Municipality of Cabagan, Province of Isabela, which is part of the First Congressional District of Isabela. The study was conducted during the School Year 2024–2025. The Cabagan District comprises twenty-six (26) barangay schools situated in various parts of the municipality. These schools are located in diverse settings, including rural areas, along highways, riverside, and within the town proper. The research locale was purposively chosen due to the researcher's direct access to the respondents and the voluntary participation of the selected schools, which ensured the feasibility and efficient conduct of the study.

Selection and Description of Respondents

A total of 286 respondents were identified, comprising 266 teachers and 20 school heads in barangay schools in Cabagan District, 1st congressional district of the province of Isabela, during School Year 2024-2025.

Table 1
Distribution of Respondents

School	Total Population of School Head	Total Population of Teachers
1. Aggub Elementary School	1	9
2. Anao Elementary School	1	10
3. Angancasilian Elementary School	1	9
4. Balasig Elementary School	0	13
5. Biwag Elementary School	1	9
6. Cabagan Science Elementary School	0	29
7. Candanum Integrated School	1	7
8. Cansan Elementary School	1	8
9. Casibarag Norte Elementary School	0	8
10. Casibarag Sur Elementary School	0	17
11. Catabayungan Elementary School	1	19
12. Cubag Integrated School	0	16
13. Garita Elementary School	1	4
14. Luquilu Elementary School	1	8
15. Mabangug Elementary School	1	7

16. Magallones Elementary School	1	9
17. Magassi Elementary School	1	10
18. Masipi Elementary School	1	13
19. Ngarag Primary School	1	4
20. Pilig Abajo Elementary School	1	6
21. Pilig Alto Elementary School	1	7
22. San Bernardo Elementary School	1	13
23. San Juan Elementary School	0	13
24. Sauí Primary School	1	2
25. Ugad Elementary School	1	11
26. Union Primary School	1	5
Total	20	266

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher asked permission from the Office of the Schools Division Superintendent to conduct this study. After the permission was granted, the researcher asked for permission from the district supervisor, which was also granted. Finally, permission was sought from the twenty (20) school heads and two hundred sixty-six (266) elementary school teachers in the Cabagan District to administer the questionnaires to the respondents in their respective schools. To ensure 100 percent retrieval of the questionnaires, the researcher personally distributed and administered the questionnaires to the respondents on weekdays.

Statistical Treatment of Data

The responses taken from the 286 respondents were collated, tallied, analyzed, and interpreted using the various statistical tools as mentioned below:

Frequency and Percentage. To analyze the profile of the respondents in terms of years in service, training attended in the last five years, and highest educational attainment.

Weighted Mean. To examine how school heads and teachers in the Cabagan district perceive the implementation of inclusive education in terms of curriculum design: competency and design, teaching methodologies and strategies, learning space and environment, learning resources, and classroom assessment. Additionally, to examine the opportunities and challenges they encounter in implementing inclusive education.

ANOVA. To assess if there is a significant effect on the perception of the school heads and teachers in implementing inclusive education, when grouped according to profile, as well as in the opportunities and challenges as perceived by the school heads and teachers, and to assess if there is a significant difference in the opportunities and challenges as perceived by the school heads and teachers.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. What is the profile of the school heads and teachers in terms of:
 - a) years in service
 - b) training attended in inclusive education in the last five years
 - c) highest educational attainment

Table 2
Profile of Respondents in terms of Years in Service

Years in Service	Administrator		Teachers		Grand Total	Percentage
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage		
31 and above	2	0.70	5	1.75	7	2.45
24-30	6	2.10	46	16.08	52	18.18
17-23	5	1.75	35	12.24	40	13.99
10-16	6	2.10	86	30.07	92	32.17
Below 10	1	0.35	94	32.87	95	33.22
Total	20	6.99	266	93.01	286	100

Table 2 presents the length of service of the respondents in Cabagan District. The result shows that the largest proportion of respondents falls in the Below 10-year category, with 33.22%, followed by those with 10-16 years of service, comprising 32.17%. This indicates that the majority of the participants are relatively early to mid-career professionals. Respondents with 20–24 years of service account for 18.18%, while those with 17-23 years of service account for 13.99%. Only a small number belong to the longest tenure category of 31 years or more, accounting for 2.45%.

Overall, the distribution shows that the workforce is largely composed of less experienced personnel, with very few long-serving employees, suggesting a relatively young professional population in terms of tenure. The findings align with the study of Jimenez (2025) which suggests that age and teaching experience significantly influence the level of implementation and the challenges encountered in inclusive education. The predominance of early-career teachers in the sample further supports this claim, indicating that teaching experience plays an important role in how educators implement and respond to inclusive education practices.

Table 3
Profile of School Heads and Teachers in terms of Training Attended in Inclusive Education in the Last Five Years

	Training	IPED	Level			Total	Percent
			DISTRICT	DIVISON	NATIONAL		
SH				5		5	1.75

		SNED		1		1	0.35	
		SPED		2		2	0.70	
	Total			8		8	2.80	
T	Training	IPED	0	13	0	13	4.55	
		SNED	6	10	1	17	5.94	
		SPED	0	2	0	2	0.70	
	Total		6	25	1	32	11.19	
Total With Training	Training	IPED	0	18	0	18	6.29	
		SNED	6	11	1	18	6.29	
		SPED	0	4	0	4	1.40	
	Total		6	33	1	40	13.99	
Total Without Training						246	86.01	
Grand Total							286	100

Table 3 presents the respondents' training in inclusive education during the last five years in Cabagan District.

The table shows that only 13.99% (40 out of 286) of respondents have received training, while the majority (86.01%) have no recorded training. Most training sessions were held at the division level, with teachers accounting for the larger share compared to school heads. Training is more concentrated in IPED and SNED, while SPED-related training remains minimal across all levels. Overall, the data indicate limited participation in training, particularly at the district and national levels, highlighting the need for expanded, more inclusive professional development opportunities.

Of the 40 respondents who attended inclusive education training within the last five years, teachers comprised the majority, followed by school heads. Nevertheless, the overall data indicate that most respondents remain untrained due to the absence of cascading or knowledge-sharing mechanisms from personnel who participated in inclusive education training programs.

The findings align with those of Benemerito (2025) which indicate that low participation in training and significant barriers to accessing training remain major concerns.

Table 4
Profile of Respondents in terms of Highest Educational Attainment

HIGHEST EDUCATIONAL ATTAINMENT	Administrators		Teachers		Total	
	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent
BACHELOR		0.00	18	6.29	18	6.29
MAED UNITS	9	3.15	175	61.19	184	64.34

MAED GRADUATES	4	1.40	53	18.53	57	19.93
MST UNITS	1	0.35	11	3.85	12	4.20
MST GRADUATES		0.00	1	0.35	1	0.35
PHD UNITS	3	1.05	8	2.80	11	3.85
PHD GRADUATES	3	1.05		0.00	3	1.05
Total	20	6.99	266	93.01	286	100

Table 4 presents the respondents' highest educational attainment. Of the 286 respondents, the majority were teachers (93.01%), while school heads accounted for only 6.99%, indicating that classroom practitioners comprised the larger portion of the sample.

In terms of qualifications, most respondents had earned MAEd units, accounting for 64.34% of the total respondents, followed by MAEd graduates at 19.93%. This shows that a large proportion of educators are actively pursuing graduate education but have not yet completed the degree. A smaller percentage held PhD units (3.85%) and PhD degrees (1.05%), suggesting limited doctoral-level qualifications among respondents. Only 6.29% held a bachelor's degree as their highest attainment.

Among school heads, graduate education was also evident, with most having completed or taken units in master's programs, while very few had doctoral qualifications. Similarly, teachers predominantly held MAEd units, indicating professional advancement efforts within the teaching workforce.

Overall, the data imply that the respondents generally possess academic preparation beyond the undergraduate level, which may contribute to their awareness and understanding of inclusive education practices.

The data aligns with the Expanded Career Progression System (Department of Education, 2025). As reflected, most respondents were classroom teachers, and many were already taking or had completed MAEd units, indicating ongoing professional development.

2. How is inclusive education being implemented in Cabagan District as perceived by the school heads and teachers in terms of:

- a) curriculum design: competency and content**
- b) teaching methodologies and strategies**
- c) learning space and environment**
- d) learning resources**
- e) classroom assessment**

Table 5
Mean Distribution on the Implementation of Inclusive Education in Cabagan District as perceived by the school heads and teachers in terms of Curriculum Design: Competency and Content

Curriculum Design: Competency and Design	Mean Administrator	Description	Mean Teachers	Description	Average Mean	Description
1. The features of an inclusive curriculum— learner-centered, appropriate, culture-sensitive, relevant, and gender-responsive.	3.50	Highly Implemented	3.41	Highly Implemented	3.45	Highly Implemented
2. Flexible enough for schools to contextualize in relation to the learner's unique needs.	3.25	Highly Implemented	3.34	Highly Implemented	3.30	Highly Implemented
3. Provides an avenue to be inclusive of the values, beliefs, practices, and knowledge systems of the learner's community	3.40	Highly Implemented	3.39	Highly Implemented	3.40	Highly Implemented
4. Promote equality and equity in developing the learners' competencies through quality differentiated instruction.	3.30	Highly Implemented	3.46	Highly Implemented	3.38	Highly Implemented
5. Adjustments can be made through simplifying content for tasks.	3.40	Highly Implemented	3.39	Highly Implemented	3.39	Highly Implemented
6. Learning materials reflect inclusivity and avoid stereotypes or biases.	3.30	Highly Implemented	3.33	Highly Implemented	3.31	Highly Implemented
7. The curriculum provides adequate resources and training for teachers to handle inclusive classrooms.	3.10	Implemented	3.24	Implemented	3.17	Implemented
8. The curriculum emphasizes skills necessary for creating an inclusive learning environment.	3.25	Highly Implemented	3.41	Highly Implemented	3.33	Highly Implemented
9. The curriculum supports teachers in developing the competency to address diverse student needs.	3.35	Highly Implemented	3.41	Highly Implemented	3.38	Highly Implemented
10. The curriculum supports differentiated instruction to cater to students with varying abilities.	3.35	Highly Implemented	3.49	Highly Implemented	3.42	Highly Implemented
Overall Mean	3.32	Highly Implemented	3.39	Highly Implemented	3.35	Highly Implemented

Table 5 presents the perceptions of school heads and teachers on the competency and content of the curriculum.

The results show that school heads perceive the competency and content as highly implemented, with an overall mean of 3.32. This indicates that the curriculum is relevant to learners with varying abilities. Teachers also rated the curriculum design as highly implemented in their schools, with an overall mean of 3.39. This shows that teachers' perceptions of the curriculum align with administrators' views, resulting in an average mean of 3.35.

The highest ratings were given to items indicating that the curriculum is relevant and learner-centered (3.45) and supports differentiated instruction (3.41) for students with varying abilities. In contrast, the lowest ratings were observed in items related to the adequacy of resources and training provided to teachers for handling inclusive classrooms (3.17). However, these were still perceived as implemented.

The findings are consistent with RA 10533 (Republic of the Philippines, 2013) which emphasizes the implementation of a learner-centered and inclusive curriculum.

Table 6
Mean Distribution on the Implementation of Inclusive Education in Cabagan District as perceived by the school heads and teachers in terms of Teaching Methodologies and Strategies

Teaching Methodologies and Strategies	Mean Administrator	Description	Mean Teachers	Description	Average Mean	Description
1. Importance of teachers' knowledge and understanding of learners' diverse characteristics and experiences as inputs to the planning and designing of learning programs.	3.50	Highly Implemented	3.42	Highly Implemented	3.46	Highly Implemented
2. Teacher Education Council (TEC) shall collaborate with other educational institutions to ensure the integration of Inclusive Education.	3.30	Highly Implemented	3.28	Highly Implemented	3.29	Highly Implemented
3. Implement an individualized education program if and when necessary.	3.30	Highly Implemented	3.18	Implemented	3.24	Highly Implemented
4. Recognize the PPST as a reference in designing interventions geared towards the professional development of teachers.	3.40	Highly Implemented	3.34	Highly Implemented	3.37	Highly Implemented
5. Visual aids, signage, and resources in the classroom represent diverse cultures, abilities, and identities.	3.40	Highly Implemented	3.35	Highly Implemented	3.37	Highly Implemented

6. Classroom displays and materials are inclusive and avoid stereotypes or biases.	3.30	Highly Implemented	3.32	Highly Implemented	3.31	Highly Implemented
7. Teachers demonstrate inclusive practices in arranging and using the learning environment.	3.50	Highly Implemented	3.43	Highly Implemented	3.46	Highly Implemented
8. Teachers are proactive in identifying and addressing barriers within the learning space.	3.30	Highly Implemented	3.41	Highly Implemented	3.36	Highly Implemented
9. The learning environment supports individualized instruction and learning plans where needed.	3.45	Highly Implemented	3.39	Highly Implemented	3.42	Highly Implemented
10. Teachers are adequately prepared to implement inclusive education practices in my classroom.	3.40	Highly Implemented	3.39	Highly Implemented	3.39	Highly Implemented
Mean	3.39	Highly Implemented	3.35	Highly Implemented	3.37	Highly Implemented

Table 6 presents the perceptions of school heads and teachers on teaching methodologies and strategies that support inclusive education.

The results show that school heads perceive inclusive teaching methodologies and strategies are highly implemented in their schools, with an overall mean of 3.39. This indicates that school heads perceive teachers as practicing a wide range of inclusive approaches that promote equity and learner participation in the classroom. At the same time, teachers also perceive that inclusive teaching methodologies and strategies are being highly implemented in their classrooms, with an overall mean of 3.35. This shows that teachers are confident in their ability to adapt instruction and create a supportive learning environment that caters to learners with diverse needs and abilities, with an average of 3.37.

The highest ratings were given to items related to teachers' knowledge and understanding of learners' diverse characteristics (3.46) and the demonstration of inclusive practices in arranging and using the learning environment (3.46). In contrast, the lowest ratings were observed in items concerning collaboration with other educational institutions (3.29) and the preparation of individualized education programs when necessary (3.24). However, these were still perceived as implemented.

The findings on teaching methodologies and strategies suggest that inclusive practices are actively implemented by teachers. This is supported by their use of differentiated interventions, including Catch-Up Fridays and the ARAL Program, which respond to learners' varied learning styles and needs, as confirmed in the interviews with school heads and teachers.

The findings align with the report of Madrigal and Ventayen's (2018) which highlights that inclusive teaching methodologies and strategies that promote equity and learner participation are consistently practiced in classrooms.

Table 7
Mean Distribution on the Implementation of Inclusive Education in Cabagan District as perceived by the school heads and teachers in terms of Learning Space and Environment

Learning Space and Environment	Mean Administrator	Description	Mean Teachers	Description	Average Mean	Description
1. The environment fosters a sense of belonging and safety for all learners.	3.45	Highly Implemented	3.43	Highly Implemented	3.44	Highly Implemented
2. Manage and sustain resources of the school and ensure that support services are available.	3.45	Highly Implemented	3.37	Highly Implemented	3.41	Highly Implemented
3. Set up resource rooms within the school to support additional needs of inclusive education.	3.25	Highly Implemented	3.27	Highly Implemented	3.26	Highly Implemented
4. Promote inclusion of with mild to moderate disability in the regular classroom or mainstreamed classes.	3.35	Highly Implemented	3.22	Implemented	3.29	Highly Implemented
5. Additional resources are needed to improve the quality of inclusive education in the school.	3.20	Implemented	3.22	Implemented	3.21	Implemented
6. Classroom layouts are flexible and adaptable to meet the needs of diverse learners.	3.35	Highly Implemented	3.26	Highly Implemented	3.30	Highly Implemented
7. Students from diverse backgrounds feel respected and included in the classroom setting.	3.50	Highly Implemented	3.39	Highly Implemented	3.45	Highly Implemented
8. Learning spaces are adapted to accommodate different learning styles and preferences.	3.35	Highly Implemented	3.32	Highly Implemented	3.33	Highly Implemented
9. The school provides accommodations, such as assistive technologies or sensory-friendly spaces, to support students with specific needs.	3.20	Implemented	3.16	Implemented	3.18	Implemented
10. The learning environment supports individualized instruction	3.40	Highly Implemented	3.29	Highly Implemented	3.34	Highly Implemented

and learning plans where needed.						
Mean	3.35	Highly Implemented	3.29	Highly Implemented	3.32	Highly Implemented

Table 7 presents the perceptions of school heads and teachers on the learning space and environment.

The results show that school heads rated the implementation of school management as highly implemented, that their schools provide a supportive learning space and environment for inclusive education, with an overall mean of 3.35. This indicates that school heads perceive the school environment as conducive to promoting inclusivity, belongingness, and safety for all learners, teachers also perceive that inclusive learning environments are being highly implemented in their schools, with an overall mean of 3.29. This shows that teachers recognize their classrooms as safe, flexible, and accommodating to learners with diverse abilities and backgrounds, with an average of 3.32.

Among the items, statements related to fostering a sense of belonging (3.44) and ensuring a safe and respectful learning environment (3.45) received the highest ratings from both groups. In contrast, items concerning the provision of additional resources (3.21) and accommodations, such as assistive technologies and sensory-friendly spaces (3.18), obtained the lowest ratings, although these were still perceived as implemented.

Interviews with school heads and teachers reveal that the learning environment fosters a sense of belonging, safety, and mutual respect among learners. Learners from varied cultural and religious backgrounds are integrated within the same classrooms without restriction. Instructional materials also represent diverse cultures, abilities, and experiences, indicating culturally responsive practices. The absence of reported bullying further suggests that learner diversity is positively accepted and effectively supported within the school community. This supports the presence of a positive and inclusive school climate, where diversity is accepted and learners feel secure within the learning environment.

The data aligns with the United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (UNCRPD) (2006), as it provides safe, inclusive, and accommodating learning environments consistent with the UNCRPD's mandate to ensure quality education for learners with disabilities in regular school settings.

Table 8
Mean Distribution on the Implementation of Inclusive Education in Cabagan District as perceived by the school heads and teachers in terms of Learning Resources

Learning Resources	Mean Administrator	Description	Mean Teachers	Description	Average Mean	Description
1. The school has the necessary physical infrastructure (ramps, accessible restrooms, etc.) to accommodate students with physical disabilities.	3.00	Implemented	3.12	Implemented	3.06	Implemented
2. The materials include examples, stories, and characters that reflect diverse cultures, abilities, and experiences.	3.35	Highly Implemented	3.24	Implemented	3.29	Highly Implemented
3. Classrooms are equipped with flexible layouts, adjustable furniture, and sensory-friendly materials.	2.95	Implemented	3.10	Implemented	3.03	Implemented
4. The school buildings follow universal design principles, including ramps, elevators, and accessible restrooms.	2.95	Implemented	2.88	Implemented	2.91	Implemented
5. Learning resources are available in multiple formats (e.g., print, digital, audio, and Braille).	3.10	Implemented	3.05	Implemented	3.08	Implemented
6. The resources support the inclusion of students from various cultural and linguistic backgrounds.	3.25	Highly Implemented	3.17	Implemented	3.21	Implemented
7. The content promotes diversity, equity, and inclusion principles.	3.30	Highly Implemented	3.28	Highly Implemented	3.29	Highly Implemented
8. The physical classroom materials are easy to manipulate or interact with for all students.	3.25	Highly Implemented	3.26	Highly Implemented	3.25	Highly Implemented
9. The learning activities encourage collaboration among students with varying abilities.	3.40	Highly Implemented	3.33	Highly Implemented	3.37	Highly Implemented
10. The content is adaptable for different learning styles and paces.	3.30	Highly Implemented	3.31	Highly Implemented	3.30	Highly Implemented
Mean	3.19	Implemented	3.17	Implemented	3.18	Implemented

Table 8 presents the perceptions of school heads and teachers regarding learning resources that support inclusive education.

The results show that both groups rated learning resources as implemented, with school heads obtaining an overall mean of 3.19 and teachers 3.17, resulting in an average mean of 3.18. This shows that school heads perceive that their schools provide adequate learning resources, such as activities to support inclusive education, indicating that while inclusive learning resources are generally available, there is still room for improvement in ensuring accessibility and adaptability for all learners. On the other hand, teachers also perceive that their schools possess adequate learning resources for inclusive education, indicating that the availability of inclusive materials and facilities is satisfactory, but acknowledge the need for further enhancement.

Items related to learning activities that promote collaboration (3.37), adaptable content (3.30), and materials that reflect diversity (3.29) received the highest ratings. In contrast, items concerning physical infrastructure (3.03) and school facilities aligned with universal design principles (2.91) obtained the lowest ratings, although these were still perceived as implemented.

The data disagrees with Lapeña et al's (2023) study as implementation of inclusive education relies heavily on the availability of teaching and learning resources, and insufficient resources negatively affect its effectiveness.

Table 9
Mean Distribution on the Implementation of Inclusive Education in Cabagan District as perceived by the school heads and teachers in terms of Classroom Assessment

Classroom Assessment	Mean Administrator	Description	Mean Teachers	Description	Average Mean	Description
1. Monitor their progress in all domains of development.	3.50	Highly Implemented	3.41	Highly Implemented	3.45	Highly Implemented
2. Assessments are designed to be accessible for students with varying abilities and needs.	3.50	Highly Implemented	3.41	Highly Implemented	3.45	Highly Implemented
3. A variety of assessment methods (e.g., written, oral, performance-based) are used to cater to different learning styles.	3.50	Highly Implemented	3.44	Highly Implemented	3.47	Highly Implemented
4. Alternative ways for students to demonstrate learning are provided when necessary.	3.50	Highly Implemented	3.33	Highly Implemented	3.42	Highly Implemented
5. Teachers shall strengthen formative assessment and provide modifications and accommodations for learners.	3.60	Highly Implemented	3.43	Highly Implemented	3.51	Highly Implemented
6. Sufficient support is available from school administration for implementing inclusive assessment practices.	3.30	Highly Implemented	3.34	Highly Implemented	3.32	Highly Implemented
7. Reflection and adjustment of assessment methods are regularly conducted to ensure inclusivity.	3.25	Highly Implemented	3.30	Highly Implemented	3.27	Highly Implemented

8. Adequate training on inclusive assessment strategies has been provided.	3.05	Implem ented	3.19	Implem ented	3.12	Implem ented
9. Assessments are free from elements that may disadvantage certain groups of students.	3.25	Highly Implem ented	3.28	Highly Implem ented	3.26	Highly Implem ented
10. Assessment results are utilized to plan and adapt teaching strategies for better inclusivity.	3.25	Highly Implem ented	3.32	Highly Implem ented	3.28	Highly Implem ented
Mean	3.37	Highly Implem ented	3.34	Highly Implem ented	3.36	Highly Implem ented

Table 9 presents that both school heads and teachers strongly agree on most classroom assessment practices.

The results show that both groups rated classroom assessment practices as highly implemented, with school heads obtaining an overall mean of 3.37 and teachers 3.34, resulting in an average mean of 3.36. This indicates that school heads highly recognize the presence of inclusive assessment systems that cater to diverse learners, while teachers perceive that inclusive classroom assessment practices are observed in their schools. This shows that teachers consistently use diverse, accessible assessment strategies to accommodate learners' individual needs.

The highest ratings were given to practices related to the use of varied and accessible assessment methods (3.47) and providing appropriate modifications and accommodations (3.51). In contrast, the lowest rating was noted for the item on adequate training in inclusive assessment strategies (3.12), which was still regarded as implemented.

The data aligns with Fuego's (2024) study, which highlights teachers' application of inclusive practices and adaptive assessment strategies to address diverse learner needs, indicating that inclusive and accessible assessment systems are consistently practiced, supporting equitable learning opportunities for all learners.

Table 10
Summary Table of the Implementation of Inclusive Education in Cabagan District

Components	Mean Administrator	Description	Mean Teachers	Description	Average Mean	Description
Curriculum Design: Competency and Content	3.32	Highly Implemented	3.39	Highly Implemented	3.35	Highly Implemented
Teaching Methodologies and Strategies	3.39	Highly Implemented	3.35	Highly Implemented	3.37	Highly Implemented
Learning Space and Environment	3.35	Highly Implemented	3.29	Highly Implemented	3.32	Highly Implemented
Learning Resources	3.19	Implemented	3.17	Implemented	3.18	Implemented

Classroom Assessment	3.37	Highly Implemented	3.34	Highly Implemented	3.36	Highly Implemented
Grand Mean	3.32	Highly Implemented	3.31	Highly Implemented	3.32	Highly Implemented

Table 10 presents the summary table of the implementation of inclusive education in Cabagan District

The result shows that the overall implementation of Inclusive Education in Cabagan District is highly implemented, as perceived by both school heads and teachers, with a grand mean of 3.32. All components—curriculum design: competency and content, teaching methodologies and strategies, learning space and environment, learning resources, and classroom assessment—were rated from implemented to highly implemented. Among the components, teaching methodologies and strategies, and classroom assessment obtained the highest average means, indicating strong inclusive practices in instructional delivery and assessment. Although the learning resources category received a slightly lower rating, it still falls under the Implemented level, suggesting the need for further enhancement in inclusive materials and facilities.

3. Is there a significant difference in the perception of the school heads and teachers in implementing inclusive education when grouped according to profile?

Table 11
Significant Difference in the Perception of the School Heads and Teachers in Implementing Inclusive Education when grouped according to Their Profile

Profile	Administrator Significant F	Decision	Remarks	Teachers Significant F	Decision	Remarks
Years in Service	.933	Accept Ho	Not Significant	.013	Reject Ho	Significant
Training attended in Inclusive Education in the last five years	.889	Accept Ho	Not Significant	.296	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Highest Educational Attainment	.698	Accept Ho	Not Significant	.517	Accept Ho	Not Significant

Table 11 reveals the significant difference in the perception of the school heads in implementing inclusive education when grouped according to profile at 0.05 level of significance.

The results indicate that there is no significant difference in perceptions among school heads when grouped according to years in service, training attended in inclusive education in the last five years, and highest educational attainment, as all computed significance values are greater than the 0.05 level of significance.

On the other hand, it also reveals the significant difference in the perception of the teachers in implementing inclusive education when grouped according to profile using 0.05 level of significance.

The results indicate that there is a significant difference in teachers' perceptions when grouped according to years in service, as the computed significance value is less than the 0.05 level of significance. In contrast, no significant differences were found when teachers were grouped according to trainings attended in inclusive education in the last five years and highest educational attainment.

The school heads' data align with the study of Palma (2004) which found moderate positive relationships among strategies, innovation, and resilience. These findings suggest that these elements work together to strengthen inclusive education. Overall, the results emphasize the need for a unified and collaborative approach to inclusive education across regions and demographic groups.

Additionally, the teachers' data align with the study of Barnes and Gaines (2015) which found that teachers at lower grade levels and those with fewer years of experience tend to have more negative attitudes toward inclusion. The study also emphasized the importance of providing pre-service and ongoing training for teachers at lower grade levels and recommended further research on this area.

4. What are the opportunities encountered by the school heads and teachers in the implementation of inclusive education in Cabagan District?

Table 12
Mean Distribution on the Opportunities encountered by the school heads and teachers in the Implementation of Inclusive Education in Cabagan District in terms of Partnerships in Inclusion

Partnerships in Inclusion	Mean Administrator	Description	Mean Teachers	Description	Average Mean	Description
1. SPED teachers were given the chance to collaborate with Project TOPI (Teaching Opportunities Prioritizing Illiteracy).	3.30	Always	3.30	Always	3.30	Always
2. The local government provides support through the inclusive learning resource center of Cabagan, initiated by the municipal Mayor.	3.40	Always	3.45	Always	3.42	Always
3. Institutionalize the implementation of Inclusive Education through Project TOPI (Teaching Opportunities Prioritizing Illiteracy).	3.35	Always	3.46	Always	3.41	Always

4. Expansion and strengthening of external linkages for coordination for Inclusive Education.	3.25	Always	3.37	Always	3.31	Always
5. NGOs were tapped as partners in resource generation to help bridge gaps in resources for inclusive education.	3.20	Often	3.31	Always	3.26	Always
6. Provision of school learning equipment, tools, and other facilities.	3.25	Always	3.23	Often	3.24	Often
7. Highlight the provision of bookshelves, tables, and chairs for the establishment of the SPED learning resource center.	3.10	Often	3.17	Often	3.14	Often
8. Innovative platforms such as Cabagan TeleRadyo for the delivery of Inclusive Education were initiated.	3.10	Often	3.21	Often	3.16	Often
9. Improved access to education through Inclusive Education.	3.25	Always	3.39	Always	3.32	Always
10. Provision of enough learning resources for Inclusive education.	3.20	Often	3.24	Always	3.22	Always
Overall Mean	3.24	Often	3.31	Always	3.28	Always

Table 12 presents how school heads and teachers rated the level of partnerships in inclusion in the implementation of inclusive education.

The results show that partnerships in inclusion were often observed by school heads, with an overall mean of 3.24, while teachers rated these partnerships as always observed, with an overall mean of 3.31, resulting in an average mean of 3.28. This indicates that school heads often observed a strong partnership between schools and other stakeholders. In contrast, teachers consistently observed the effective implementation of partnerships for inclusion within their schools, characterized by strong and active collaboration among various stakeholders to support inclusive education initiatives.

The highest ratings were given to items related to collaboration with local government units, institutionalization of inclusive education initiatives such as Project TOPI (3.41), and improved access to education through ILRC (3.42). In contrast, lower ratings were observed in items concerning the provision of physical learning resources for SPED learning resource centers (3.14) and the initiation of innovative platforms for delivering inclusive education (3.16), although these were still frequently observed.

The study aligns with Perez's (2019) study which highlights the vital role of NGOs in supporting inclusive education, as evidenced by the strong and active partnerships observed between schools and various stakeholders in implementing inclusive education initiatives.

Table 13
Mean Distribution on the Opportunities encountered by the school heads and teachers in the implementation of Inclusive Education in Cabagan District in terms of Governance Support

Governance Support	Mean Administrator	Description	Mean Teachers	Description	Average Mean	Description
1. National planning standards shall be responsive to the diversity of learning contexts.	3.35	Always	3.33	Always	3.34	Always
2. Consider the specific needs to realize inclusive education in the planning and programming of resources.	3.40	Always	3.31	Always	3.36	Always
3. Special Education Fund (SEF) and other available local resources were utilized to support Inclusive education.	3.30	Always	3.24	Often	3.27	Always
4. Internal and external stakeholders were involved in the advocacy of Inclusive education.	3.45	Always	3.31	Always	3.38	Always
5. Advocate for stronger legislation to support inclusive education.	3.35	Always	3.33	Always	3.34	Always
6. Policies related to inclusive education are duly supported by the Local Government Unit.	3.50	Always	3.43	Always	3.46	Always
7. Inclusive education is part of the School Improvement Plan.	3.50	Always	3.44	Always	3.47	Always
8. Regular assessments and reviews to ensure the effectiveness of inclusive education policies.	3.40	Always	3.38	Always	3.39	Always
9. Both internal and external are involved in decision making involving the implementation of inclusive education.	3.40	Always	3.37	Always	3.38	Always
10. There is adequate funding allocated to support inclusive education initiatives.	3.30	Always	3.21	Often	3.26	Always
Overall Mean	3.40	Always	3.33	Always	3.36	Always

Table 13 presents how school heads and teachers rated the level of governance support in the implementation of inclusive education.

The results show that both groups rated governance support as always observed, with school heads obtaining an overall mean of 3.40 and teachers 3.33, resulting in an average mean of 3.36. This indicates that governance structures and policies are perceived to support the implementation of inclusive education effectively.

The highest ratings were given to items related to the inclusion of inclusive education in the School Improvement Plan (3.47), strong local government support for inclusive education policies (3.46), and regular assessments and reviews of inclusive education programs (3.39). In contrast, comparatively lower ratings were observed in items concerning the utilization of the Special Education Fund (3.27) and the adequacy of funding allocated to support inclusive education initiatives (3.26). However, these were still perceived as always observed.

The data contradicts Kilag et al.'s (2004) study, which asserts that while parents, communities, LGUs, and NGOs play a crucial role in supporting learners with special needs, coordination and collaboration among these groups remain limited.

Table 14
Mean Distribution on the Opportunities encountered by the school heads and teachers in the implementation of Inclusive Education in Cabagan District in terms of Teacher Professional Development

III. Teacher Professional Development	Mean Administrator	Description	Mean Teachers	Description	Average Mean	Description
1. Schools or districts provide adequate opportunities for ongoing professional development in inclusive education.	3.40	Always	3.37	Always	3.39	Always
2. Provides effective strategies for differentiating instruction for diverse learners.	3.45	Always	3.43	Always	3.44	Always
3. Improve the ability to assess and monitor the progress of students with diverse learning needs.	3.60	Always	3.42	Always	3.51	Always
4. Teachers acquired varied teaching strategies for inclusive education from different professional development programs.	3.50	Always	3.42	Always	3.46	Always
5. Offer workshops on behavior management strategies for inclusive education	3.25	Always	3.35	Always	3.30	Always
6. Teachers are confident enough to teach learners with disabilities.	3.40	Always	3.35	Always	3.37	Always
7. Offer support for the development activities of inclusive education to improve teaching practices.	3.45	Always	3.35	Always	3.40	Always
8. Address the latest research and best practices in inclusive education.	3.20	Often	3.27	Always	3.24	Often

9. Focus on providing practical, classroom-based strategies for inclusive teaching.	3.45	Always	3.36	Always	3.40	Always
10. Teachers are well equipped with the required (KSA) knowledge, skills, and attitude to address social-emotional learning needs in inclusive classrooms.	3.45	Always	3.44	Always	3.44	Always
Overall Mean	3.42	Always	3.38	Always	3.40	Always

Table 14 presents how school heads and teachers rated the level of teacher professional development in the implementation of inclusive education.

The results show that both groups rated teacher professional development as always observed, with school heads averaging 3.42 and teachers 3.38, resulting in an overall mean of 3.40. This indicates that school heads consistently observe sufficient and effective professional development initiatives that support teachers in implementing inclusive education practices. Similarly, teachers always observe professional development opportunities, indicating a highly favorable level of provision for inclusive education.

The highest ratings were given to items related to teachers' improved ability to assess and monitor learners' progress (3.51), acquisition of varied teaching strategies for inclusive education (3.46), preparedness in terms of knowledge, skills, and attitudes (3.44), and provision of effective strategies (3.44). In contrast, a comparatively lower rating was observed in the item concerning the application of the latest research and best practices in inclusive education, with a mean of 3.24, although these were still frequently observed.

The data aligns with Bautista and Cayabyab's (2025) study which highlights the need for professional development that is both culturally responsive and grounded in the real-world context of international schools. It underscores the importance of bridging the gap between positive attitudes toward inclusion and actual classroom practices through specialized training, strong leadership support, and policies that reflect the multicultural character of these schools.

Table 15
Summary Table of Opportunities Encountered in the Implementation of Inclusive Education in Cabagan District

Components	Mean Administrator	Description	Mean Teachers	Description	Average Mean	Description
Partnerships in Inclusion	3.24	Often	3.31	Always	3.28	Always
Governance Support	3.40	Always	3.33	Always	3.36	Always
Teacher Professional Development	3.42	Always	3.38	Always	3.40	Always

Overall Mean	3.35	Always	3.34	Always	3.35	Always
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Table 15 presents the summary table of the opportunities encountered in the implementation of inclusive education in Cabagan District

The result shows that opportunities encountered during the implementation of Inclusive Education in Cabagan District were always observed, with a mean of 3.35. Governance support and teacher professional development obtained the highest ratings, suggesting strong institutional backing and continuous capacity-building for teachers. While partnerships in inclusion were also positively rated, they received a relatively lower mean, indicating an area where further strengthening of external linkages may enhance inclusive education implementation.

5. How serious are the challenges encountered by the school heads and the teachers in the implementation of inclusive education in Cabagan District?

Table 16
Mean Distribution on the challenges encountered by the school heads and the teachers in the implementation of inclusive education in Cabagan District in terms of Teacher Preparedness

Teacher Preparedness	Mean Administrator	Description	Mean Teachers	Description	Average Mean	Description
1. Lack of confidence in teachers' abilities to implement inclusive education practices effectively.	2.35	Moderately Serious	2.34	Moderately Serious	2.35	Moderately Serious
2. Insufficient professional development opportunities hinder teachers from managing the diverse needs of learners.	2.35	Moderately Serious	2.43	Moderately Serious	2.39	Moderately Serious
3. The training provided to teachers is often inadequate for addressing the needs of learners.	2.55	Serious	2.50	Serious	2.53	Serious
4. Lack of preparedness to manage the complexities of inclusive education due to limited professional opportunities.	2.55	Serious	2.39	Moderately Serious	2.47	Moderately Serious
5. Inadequate support in differentiated instruction and inclusive pedagogical strategies.	2.50	Serious	2.39	Moderately Serious	2.45	Moderately Serious
6. The lack of time and huge class size prevent many instructors from effectively	2.55	Serious	2.53	Serious	2.54	Serious

implementing proper ideas of inclusive education.						
7. Feelings of being overwhelmed by the demands of inclusive education.	2.35	Moderately Serious	2.48	Moderately Serious	2.42	Moderately Serious
8. Lack of resources as a significant barrier to implementing inclusive education.	2.70	Serious	2.61	Serious	2.65	Serious
9. Lack of clear guidelines for inclusive education implementation in schools.	2.45	Moderately Serious	2.53	Serious	2.49	Moderately Serious
10. Challenges in maintaining high academic standards in an inclusive classroom.	2.50	Serious	2.68	Serious	2.59	Serious
Overall Mean	2.49	Moderately Serious	2.49	Moderately Serious	2.49	Moderately Serious

Table 16 presents how school heads and teachers rated the level of teacher preparedness in implementing inclusive education.

The results show that both school heads and teachers rated the challenges related to teacher preparedness as moderately serious, resulting in an overall mean of 2.49.

Items related to lack of resources (2.65), insufficient training (2.53), time constraints, large class sizes, maintaining high academic standards (2.59), and difficulties in meeting diverse learner needs (2.54) are perceived as more serious concerns, while issues related to teachers' confidence (2.35) were perceived as less serious. Overall, the findings indicate that challenges related to teacher preparedness are present but not perceived as highly severe.

The data aligns with Cruz's (2016) study, as both indicate that challenges related to teacher preparedness persist despite generally positive attitudes toward inclusive education.

Table 17
Mean Distribution on the challenges encountered by the school heads and the teachers in the implementation of inclusive education in Cabagan District in terms of Resource Availability and Infrastructure

Resource Availability and Infrastructure	Mean Administrator	Description	Mean Teachers	Description	Average Mean	Description
1. Unavailability of resources, such as learning materials and assistive technologies for supporting inclusive education.	2.80	Serious	2.70	Serious	2.75	Serious
2. Inadequate physical infrastructure, including ramps and	2.65	Serious	2.74	Serious	2.69	Serious

accessible restrooms, impedes the inclusion of students with disabilities.						
3. Inclusive education policies are not consistently implemented due to a lack of funding and resources.	2.60	Serious	2.68	Serious	2.64	Serious
4. Many schools are not well-equipped to provide the necessary individual support for learners.	2.75	Serious	2.65	Serious	2.70	Serious
5. Schools in conflict-affected areas are particularly disadvantaged in learning resources.	2.55	Serious	2.62	Serious	2.59	Serious
6. Scarcity of necessary resources, such as learning materials, creates gaps in promoting inclusive practices.	2.70	Serious	2.64	Serious	2.67	Serious
7. Insufficient resources cause teachers to be left in navigating the complexities of inclusion with little institutional support.	2.60	Serious	2.68	Serious	2.64	Serious
8. The ratio of support staff (e.g., teaching assistants, counselors) to students in inclusive settings is insufficient.	2.70	Serious	2.75	Serious	2.73	Serious
9. The curriculum in inclusive classrooms is not flexible enough to accommodate the learning styles of all students.	2.50	Serious	2.61	Serious	2.55	Serious
10. Schools often lack the financial resources necessary to implement inclusive education practices effectively.	2.60	Serious	2.67	Serious	2.63	Serious
Overall Mean	2.65	Serious	2.67	Serious	2.66	Serious

Table 17 presents how school heads and teachers rated the level of resource availability and infrastructure in the implementation of inclusive education.

The results show that both school heads and teachers rated challenges related to resources and infrastructure as serious, with school heads obtaining an overall mean of 2.65 and teachers 2.67, resulting in an average mean of 2.66. This indicates that both groups perceive resource availability and infrastructure constraints as major factors affecting the successful implementation of inclusive practices.

The findings indicate that issues related to the availability of learning materials (2.70), assistive technologies (2.75), physical infrastructure (2.69), and support personnel (2.73) are consistently perceived as serious challenges. In contrast, curriculum flexibility is perceived as a lesser concern (2.55). Overall, the results suggest that limitations in resources and infrastructure remain a persistent concern in the implementation of inclusive education.

The data aligns with the findings of Kilag et al's (2024) study which notes that gaps persist in translating policies into meaningful practice. Insufficient infrastructure, limited

resources, and a shortage of trained personnel continue to hinder the achievement of inclusive education objectives. Moreover, inadequate school facilities, overcrowded classrooms, and weak support systems limit the full participation of students with disabilities in regular classroom settings.

Table 18
Mean Distribution on the challenges encountered by the school heads and the teachers in the implementation of inclusive education in Cabagan District in terms of Policy and Implementation

Policy and Implementation	Mean Administrator	Description	Mean Teachers	Description	Average Mean	Description
1. Policies often fail to translate into practice at the school level.	2.50	Serious	2.56	Serious	2.53	Serious
2. Unclear guidelines for implementing inclusive education policies contribute to inconsistent practices in schools.	2.50	Serious	2.58	Serious	2.54	Serious
3. There is a significant gap between national inclusive education policies and their practical implementation at the local level.	2.65	Serious	2.64	Serious	2.65	Serious
4. The lack of accountability mechanisms complicates the enforcement of inclusive education policies in schools.	2.60	Serious	2.61	Serious	2.60	Serious
5. Limited comprehension of regulations, issues, and personalized assistance in the area.	2.65	Serious	2.61	Serious	2.63	Serious
6. Overcrowded classrooms hinder the effective implementation of inclusive education practices.	2.75	Serious	2.77	Serious	2.76	Serious
7. The lack of understanding among stakeholders about the benefits of inclusive education for all students.	2.60	Serious	2.67	Serious	2.64	Serious
8. Biases and stigma within the school community hinder the implementation of inclusive education practices.	2.60	Serious	2.62	Serious	2.61	Serious
9. Assessment practices in schools are inflexible and fail to accommodate students with diverse learning needs.	2.75	Serious	2.56	Serious	2.66	Serious
10. Insufficient data collection and analysis to evaluate the	2.70	Serious	2.59	Serious	2.65	Serious

effectiveness of inclusive education policies.						
Overall Mean	2.63	Serious	2.62	Serious	2.63	Serious

Table 18 presents how school heads and teachers rated the level of policy and implementation in the delivery of inclusive education. The results show that school heads obtained an overall mean of 2.63, while teachers obtained 2.62, both described as Serious, resulting in an average mean of 2.63. This indicates that they share a similar perception with school heads, namely that policy and implementation barriers significantly affect inclusive education practices.

Among the items, challenges related to policy implementation, including policy translation (2.65), assessment practices (2.66), classroom conditions (2.76), and data utilization (2.65), are consistently perceived as serious concerns by both groups. Overall, the results suggest that policy-related issues significantly affect the effective delivery of inclusive education.

The data appear to contradict the localized policy implemented in Cabagan. Project TOPI (Teaching Opportunities Prioritizing Illiteracy) (2025), initiated by the Municipal Mayor, functions as a local government literacy intervention aimed at supporting learners at risk, particularly non-readers and frustration readers. Learners requiring inclusion support are likewise accommodated through the establishment of the Cabagan Inclusive Learning Resource Center (ILRC) (2025). In coordination with reading coordinators, the LGU conducts pull-out remediation sessions and monitors learner progress through reading level assessments.

Table 19
Mean Distribution on the challenges encountered by the school heads and the teachers in the implementation of inclusive education in Cabagan District in terms of Collaboration

Collaboration Between Teachers and Parents	Mean Administrator	Description	Mean Teachers	Description	Average Mean	Description
1. Weak collaboration between teachers and parents impedes the successful implementation of inclusive education.	2.60	Serious	2.59	Serious	2.60	Serious
2. Poor communication between teachers and parents in achieving inclusive education goals.	2.55	Serious	2.60	Serious	2.58	Serious
3. Limited involvement of parents in decision-making processes regarding their child's education.	2.70	Serious	2.64	Serious	2.67	Serious
4. Lack of communication, understanding, or support from families can hinder effective	2.65	Serious	2.67	Serious	2.66	Serious

implementation of inclusive education.						
5. Negative perceptions can hinder parents' willingness to embrace inclusive education initiatives.	2.55	Serious	2.70	Serious	2.62	Serious
6. Teachers and parents struggle to find mutually convenient times for meetings or discussions about the child's progress.	2.60	Serious	2.64	Serious	2.62	Serious
7. Limited resources at school and in the home environment prevent teachers and parents from effectively supporting inclusive education.	2.55	Serious	2.71	Serious	2.63	Serious
8. Lack of trust between teachers and parents, which affects their ability to work collaboratively for the benefit of the child.	2.55	Serious	2.50	Serious	2.53	Serious
9. Information regarding the child's needs and school performance is not readily accessible or understandable to parents.	2.45	Serious	2.56	Serious	2.50	Serious
10. Both teachers and parents are unclear about their respective roles in supporting the child's learning in an inclusive environment.	2.35	Serious	2.50	Serious	2.43	Moderately Serious
Overall Mean	2.56	Serious	2.61	Serious	2.58	Serious

Table 19 presents how school heads and teachers rated the level of collaboration. The results show that school heads obtained an overall mean of 2.56, while teachers obtained 2.61, both described as Serious, resulting in an average mean of 2.58. This indicates that both groups recognize that the weak collaboration between teachers and parents poses a considerable challenge to achieving effective inclusive education, but it still occurs to some degree.

This indicates that challenges related to communication (2.66), parental involvement (2.67), and availability of resources in both school and home settings (2.63) are consistently perceived as serious concerns. Overall, the findings suggest that limitations in teacher–parent collaboration remain a significant challenge in the effective implementation of inclusive education.

This data aligns with the findings of Beltran et al's (2025) study which identifies weak collaboration between teachers and parents as a key issue in addressing student needs. The study recommends that the Department of Education ensure proper documentation of learners with special needs to improve resource allocation and implement awareness campaigns that strengthen stakeholder roles in promoting inclusive education.

Table 20
Summary Table of Challenges Encountered in the Implementation of Inclusive Education in Cabagan District

Components	Mean Administrator	Description	Mean Teachers	Description	Average Mean	Description
Teacher Preparedness	2.49	Moderately Serious	2.49	Moderately Serious	2.49	Moderately Serious
Resource Availability and Infrastructure	2.65	Serious	2.67	Serious	2.66	Serious
Policy and Implementation	2.63	Serious	2.62	Serious	2.63	Serious
Collaboration with Teachers and Parents	2.56	Serious	2.61	Serious	2.58	Serious
Overall Mean	2.58	Serious	2.60	Serious	2.59	Serious

Table 20 presents the summary table of the challenges encountered in the implementation of inclusive education in Cabagan District

The results show that the challenges encountered in implementing Inclusive Education in Cabagan District were generally rated as Serious, with an overall mean of 2.59. Among the identified challenges, resource availability and infrastructure, policy and implementation, and collaboration between teachers and parents were perceived as serious concerns. Teacher preparedness, while still a concern, was rated as moderately serious, indicating that although teachers possess some level of readiness, further capacity-building and support are needed.

6. Is there a significant difference in the opportunities and challenges as perceived by the school heads and teachers?

Table 21
Significant Difference in the Opportunities and Challenges as encountered by the School Heads and Teachers

Variables	Group	Mean	Significance F	Decision	Remarks
OPPORTUNITIES IN INCLUSIVE EDUCATION	School Heads	3.35	.89	Accept Ho	Not Significant
	Teachers	3.34			
	School Heads	2.58	.72	Accept Ho	Not Significant

CHALLENGES IN INCLUSIVE EDUCATION	Teachers	2.60		
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Table 21 reveals a significant difference in the opportunities and challenges in inclusive education as perceived by school heads and teachers, as determined by an Analysis of Variance F-test at the .05 level of significance.

The results show that there is no significant difference between the perceptions of school heads and teachers regarding opportunities in inclusive education and the challenges encountered, based on the Analysis of Variance F-test at the 0.05 level of significance. The computed significance values for both opportunities and challenges were greater than 0.05, leading to the acceptance of the null hypothesis. This indicates that school heads and teachers share similar perceptions of the opportunities available and the challenges encountered in implementing inclusive education.

The data aligns with the findings of Manguilimotan et al's (2024) study that says the respondents demonstrated a highly positive perception of inclusive education, and no significant differences were found between their demographic profiles and their views on inclusion. Overall, the results indicate that respondents feel confident and optimistic about managing inclusive classrooms.

Conclusions

Based on the findings, the following conclusions were deduced.

1. Profile of the respondents in terms of:

a) Years in Service

In conclusion, the distribution of respondents in terms of years in service indicates that the organization is primarily composed of early- to mid-career professionals, with only a minimal proportion of long-tenured personnel. This suggests a relatively young workforce in terms of professional experience. Such a composition may imply strong potential for growth and development, while also highlighting the need for continuous mentoring, capacity-building initiatives, and institutional knowledge transfer from more experienced members.

b) Training attended in Inclusive Education in the last five years

In conclusion, the training participation in inclusive education remains limited, as the majority of respondents have not received formal training. This suggests a need to expand professional development opportunities at various levels to strengthen the knowledge and competencies of school heads and teachers in implementing inclusive education effectively.

c) . Highest Educational Attainment

In conclusion, the school heads demonstrate a strong commitment to professional and academic advancement, as evidenced by their graduate-level qualifications. Their advanced educational attainment may contribute positively to their leadership capacity, decision-making skills, and effectiveness in managing and implementing school programs, including inclusive education initiatives.

While, teachers demonstrate a strong commitment to continuing professional development, as reflected in their pursuit of graduate education. Their advanced academic preparation may enhance their instructional competence and capacity to implement school programs effectively, including inclusive education initiatives.

2. Perception of the school heads and teachers in the implementation of Inclusive Education in Cabagan District in terms of:

a) Curriculum design: Competency and Content

In conclusion, the respondents perceive the curriculum as generally responsive and inclusive of learners' needs. Nevertheless, notable deficiencies remain in terms of professional development opportunities and the availability of sufficient instructional resources necessary for effectively managing inclusive classrooms. Considering the diverse and complex needs of learners, continuous teacher training and adequate resource provision are crucial to strengthening the effective implementation of inclusive education.

b) Teaching Methodologies and Strategies

In conclusion, the respondents recognize the importance of teachers' knowledge and understanding of learners' backgrounds as essential inputs in the planning and design of learning programs, and they acknowledge that teachers demonstrate inclusive practices in the classroom. However, there remain notable gaps in collaboration with other educational institutions and in the development and implementation of Individualized Education Programs (IEPs). These findings underscore the need to thoroughly understand the upbringing and diverse backgrounds of learners to appropriately address their educational needs, as well as the importance of strengthening partnerships with government agencies and educational institutions to broaden knowledge-sharing and enhance the effective implementation of inclusive education in inclusive classrooms.

c) Learning Space and Environment

In conclusion, the respondents perceive the learning environment as safe and healthy for all learners, regardless of diversity, and report feeling respected and included. However, there are identified limitations within the Cabagan District in terms of available resources, particularly assistive technologies and sensory-friendly spaces. These findings underscore the importance of providing an inclusive learning environment that supports the learning processes of learners with varying needs, enabling them to

effectively address their educational requirements and actively participate alongside their peers despite their specific needs.

d) Learning Resources

In conclusion, the respondents perceive that learning activities and content promote collaboration and adaptability among diverse learners; however, there remains a need for improvement in the provision of physical infrastructure and in ensuring that school buildings adhere to universal design principles. These findings highlight that the learning experiences of learners can be further enhanced when inclusive classrooms are equipped with sufficient instructional resources and when all schools comply with policies on school infrastructure aligned with universal design principles to ensure accessibility for all learners.

e) Classroom Assessment

In conclusion, the respondents perceive that teachers utilize formative assessment and a variety of assessment methods to provide appropriate accommodations and address the diverse needs of learners. However, the need for adequate training in inclusive assessment practices remains a priority. These findings underscore the importance of providing capacity-building programs focused on inclusive assessment to enhance teachers' competencies in facilitating modifications and in designing and adapting assessment strategies that promote greater inclusivity.

3. Significant difference in the perception of the school heads and teachers in implementing inclusive education: when grouped according to profile.

a) Significant Difference in the Perception of the School Heads in Implementing Inclusive Education when grouped according to Their Profile

In conclusion, there is no difference in the perspectives of the school heads regarding the implementation of inclusive education in the Cabagan District, regardless of their length of service, the number of trainings they have attended, or their educational attainment. This reflects that despite their differences in these aspects, they share a common idea and perspective toward the implementation of inclusive education, as they are guided by the same goals, policies, and strategies in carrying out the said program in their respective schools.

b) Significant Difference in the Perception of the Teachers in implementing Inclusive Education when grouped according to Their Profile

In conclusion, there is no difference in teachers' perspectives on inclusive education regardless of the trainings they have attended or their educational attainment; however, differences are evident in terms of length of teaching experience. Teachers who have been in service longer demonstrate greater awareness and a broader understanding of the program compared to those who are relatively new in the profession. This indicates that longer years of service contribute to deeper knowledge of inclusive education and its

implementation, unlike novice teachers who still need to participate in trainings to further enhance their understanding of the program.

4. Opportunities encountered by the school heads and teachers in the implementation of inclusive education in Cabagan District in terms of:

a) Partnerships in Inclusion

In conclusion, the findings highlight the significant role of the local government unit in supporting inclusive education through initiatives such as the Inclusive Learning Resource Center (ILRC) and Project TOPI (Teaching Opportunities Prioritizing Illiteracy), both initiated by the municipal mayor. These programs demonstrate active collaboration among stakeholders and strengthen community participation through information platforms such as Cabagan TeleRadyo, which helps increase public awareness of inclusive education initiatives. However, there remains a need to further enhance the provision of adequate learning resources and to develop more innovative delivery platforms to better support program implementation. Ensuring the availability of appropriate resources within the ILRC is essential for effectively addressing diverse learning needs and promoting the holistic development of learners.

b) Governance Support

In conclusion, the respondents recognize active collaboration with the local government unit in supporting policies related to inclusive education and acknowledge that the program is integrated into the School Improvement Plan (SIP) as part of long-term planning. However, adequate support in terms of funding and proper allocation remains a critical concern. These findings suggest that the effective implementation of inclusive education is strengthened through sustained external collaboration and can be further enhanced when sufficient financial resources are allocated to address existing resource-related gaps.

c) Teacher Professional Development

In conclusion, teacher professional development significantly contributes to the effective implementation of inclusive education by improving instructional strategies, assessment practices, and teacher confidence in addressing diverse learner needs. While existing initiatives provide strong support for inclusive teaching, the limited engagement with current research and emerging best practices indicates the need for continuous and sustained professional learning. Strengthening access to up-to-date, research-based knowledge will further enhance teachers' capacity and ensure the long-term effectiveness of inclusive education implementation.

5. Challenges encountered by the school heads and the teachers in the implementation of inclusive education in Cabagan District in terms of:

a) Teacher Preparedness

In conclusion, challenges related to teacher preparedness moderately influence the implementation of inclusive education. Although teachers and school heads generally view teachers as capable of carrying out inclusive practices, ongoing constraints—such as limited resources, time demands, large class sizes, insufficient training, and the pressure to maintain high academic standards—continue to impede effective implementation. Therefore, while teacher preparedness is not considered a major barrier, addressing these systemic and capacity-related concerns remains essential to strengthen inclusive education practices and improve classroom implementation.

b) Resource Availability and Infrastructure

In conclusion, the respondents identify limitations in resources, funding, and infrastructure as the primary barriers to the effective implementation of inclusive education, while curriculum flexibility is perceived as a lesser concern. These findings indicate that the main challenges are structural and financial rather than curricular in nature. This suggests that without adequate learning resources, appropriate physical infrastructure, and sufficient support staff, meeting the demands of inclusive education becomes difficult, as its full implementation cannot be achieved with limited material preparation and support systems.

c) Policy and Implementation

In conclusion, policy- and implementation-related challenges substantially hinder the effective practice of inclusive education. Although formal policies exist, school heads and teachers encounter persistent difficulties in operationalizing them, particularly in ensuring accountability, managing classroom conditions, and effectively utilizing assessment and data systems. These gaps indicate that the presence of policy alone is insufficient; strengthened implementation mechanisms and operational support are necessary to achieve consistent and effective inclusive education at the school level.

d) Collaboration

In conclusion, difficulties in teacher–parent collaboration hinder the effective implementation of inclusive education. Weak communication, limited parental involvement in decision-making, and insufficient mutual support reduce coordinated efforts in addressing learners' needs. Strengthening collaborative engagement between schools and families is therefore necessary to support consistent and effective inclusive education practices.

6. Significant difference in the opportunities and challenges as perceived by the school heads and teachers.

In conclusion, the study demonstrates that school heads and teachers share comparable perceptions regarding the opportunities and challenges of inclusive education. The findings further reveal that years of service, participation in inclusive education trainings, and educational attainment do not significantly influence these

perceptions. Regardless of position or professional experience, respondents exhibit a shared understanding of inclusive education and a collective commitment to strengthening inclusive practices. Overall, the results highlight a unified effort among school heads and teachers to ensure equitable and inclusive learning opportunities for all learners.

Recommendations

1. To strengthen teacher preparedness, it is recommended that schools may integrate short inclusive education discussions during monthly LAC sessions and organize a shared repository of adapted worksheets and assessment formats to reduce preparation time. Flexible remediation schedules, such as brief support periods after class or during homeroom, may also be implemented to help manage large class sizes and limited instructional time while maintaining academic standards.
2. To address resource and infrastructure limitations, it is recommended that the school may coordinate with the LGU and community stakeholders to obtain recycled learning materials, usable equipment, and volunteer support personnel. Low-cost classroom modifications, such as visual labels, designated learning corners, and seating adjustments, may also be implemented using available materials to improve accessibility. In addition, inclusive education resources may be prioritized in the School Improvement Plan (SIP) to support the gradual procurement of essential materials.
3. To improve policy implementation, it is recommended that the school may conduct a start-of-year orientation on inclusive education procedures, including referral flow, documentation, and teacher responsibilities. A brief monthly case conference may also be organized to discuss learners requiring support and coordinate appropriate interventions. In addition, the school head may utilize a simple monitoring checklist to track accommodations provided and learner progress, ensuring consistent accountability in practice.
4. To strengthen teacher–parent collaboration, it is recommended that the school may conduct quarterly parent orientations on inclusive education and provide a simple home support guide containing suggested practice activities. Teachers may also establish a regular communication channel, such as a communication notebook or messaging group, to give weekly updates on learner progress. Parents may be encouraged to participate in intervention planning during conferences or card distribution days, while a designated parent focal person or PTA volunteer can help coordinate concerns and facilitate continuous school–home communication.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher ensured that this study complied with established ethical standards in the conduct of research. Prior to data gathering, permission was secured from the concerned school authorities to conduct the study in the selected public elementary schools in Cabagan District. Participation of the respondents was entirely voluntary, and they were properly informed of the purpose, nature, and significance of the study before

taking part. The researcher observed the principle of informed consent by clearly explaining the objectives of the research and assuring the respondents that their participation was voluntary. They were also informed that they could withdraw from the study at any time without penalty or negative consequences.

Confidentiality and anonymity were strictly maintained throughout the research process. No personal identifiers of the respondents were disclosed in any part of the study, and all information gathered was used solely for academic purposes. The data collected were handled with utmost care and were not altered, fabricated, or misrepresented in any way. Furthermore, the researcher upheld honesty, integrity, and respect in the analysis and interpretation of the findings. All sources used in the study were properly acknowledged to avoid plagiarism. In conducting this research, the welfare, dignity, and rights of the respondents were given the highest importance at all times.

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